

I Think Oliver Stone May Sue My University

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Universities no longer have mission statements. They have vision slogans. The slogans are part of university branding, which has replaced university mission [1].

Branding removes the need for complete sentences. Slogans now declare visions of higher education. Often, they are reduced to one word. At my university, banners with the word BOLD appeared all over campus. One might imagine the goal of branding is to stand out, to be unique, to be original. Not so. At the modern university it's about homogenization ("we have what they have so you should apply here"). A web search with the words 'bold' and 'university' shows how it works. A selection of hits that search got me:

- Bold Hearts. Brilliant Minds. (UC Riverside)
- BOLD Levels of Engagement (Belmont University)
- BE BOLD. Shape the Future. (New Mexico State)
- A University For the Bold (William & Mary)
- Be BOLD (University of Arkansas)
- Be Blue. Be Gold. BE BOLD (University of Nebraska)
- Be Your Bold Self (University of St. Thomas)
- Brave and Bold (University of Idaho)
- Bold Path Forward (Idaho State)
- Be Bold (Rice University)

So much for originality.

There is irony in universities, that promote writing skills for students, abandoning complete sentences in favor of bullet point ad-speak and originality in favor of plagiarizing each other. The irony hit even closer for me as my university upped the vision ante.

Homogenized ad-speak visions allow for upgrades. My university recently went through one of these. The buzzword BOLD was replaced by a bolder buzzword: MOMENToUS [2].

My university 'partnered' with McKinsey and Co. to develop its vision upgrade and budget transformation model ('partnered' is newspeak for 'hired'). The budget model is a variant of 'bums in seats', which started in the UK and spread to Australia (the Americanized phrase replaces bums with butts). Individual department funding is based on dollar values put on the heads of students who attend classes offered by a department. The model has a history of leading to faculty and staff layoffs [3]. That McKinsey and Co. would suggest it is not surprising - they have a history of providing efficiency advice that leads to firing at the worker level and funneling of resources upward to executive leadership [4,5].

With that background in place, we can get to the title of this essay. McKinsey and Co. have not been shy in putting out slick documents about how universities should transform themselves [6]. They speak of 'moments' and how universities should seize them. Its generic advice. I was aware of this when I read the slick document from my own university

announcing the new MOMENToUS vision and budget model designed “by us, for us” [7]. Early in the document we are presented with:

THERE ARE MOMENTS THAT CHANGE THE FUTURE.
THIS IS THAT MOMENT FOR OUR UNIVERSITY.

Gotta love the all caps writing style.

I felt I had heard this before. I tracked it back to the 1987 movie Wall Street, directed by Oliver Stone who also co-wrote the screen play. The pertinent quote is spoken by Bud Fox (played by Charlie Sheen):

“Life all comes down to a few moments. This is one of them.”

So much for originality.

Call it plagiarism or call it homage. It comes with an added irony that connects to McKinsey and Co. and the butts in seats model having a history of generating layoffs. Bud Fox speaks the line before he goes into Gordon Gekko's office to try and get a job with him. In the meeting Bud winds up selling out his father and the company his father works for just so he can get a job as a trader with Gekko, who is a corporate raider and will later try to sell off the company so that everyone who works for it will lose their jobs. Gekko's most famous speech has the memorable lines "I am not a destroyer of companies. I am a liberator of them! The point is, ladies and gentlemen, that greed, for lack of a better word, is good."

So, there it is Mr. Stone, on the off chance you may read this: My university owes you a writers' fee. If they refuse, then you can sue them.

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Left: A photo of the academic quad at my university - banners won't do, branding now requires lawn art (*photo: Cin-Ty Lee*). Right: An enhancement of the photo. The new vision plan makes bold predictions of what will happen ten years in the future. I searched for a word that expresses this recent trend in academia and found 'preposterism' in an article titled *Universities' Research Imperative: Paying the Price for Perverse Incentives*, by Susan Haack [8].

Notes and References

- [1] Mission is about what you're doing now and how you are facilitating that. Vision is about what you would like to do in the future. Branding is about creating an identity that, in principle, helps customers/consumers choose your company over the competition.
- [2] A link to the in house announcement of the new vision: <https://news.rice.edu/news/2024/momentous-personalized-scale-global-impact-rice-unveils-new-strategic-plan> . MOMENToUS is meant to be read as MOMENT To US. That type of creativity is what earns advertising consultants the big bucks.
- [3] With a colleague, I have written about these types of models and their effects. The essays, although tongue-in-cheek, have pertinent references for those interested: <https://zenodo.org/records/12746825>
- [4] Some insights about McKinsey and Company: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AiOUojVd6xQ>
- [5] My university administration no longer refers to itself as administration. The newspeak is academic leadership. That change of terminology is in keeping with advice from consulting companies like McKinsey and Co., who know that titles matter: <https://zenodo.org/records/13893732>
- [6] The McKinsey playbook on 'how to transform higher education institutions' can be found at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-to-transform-higher-education-institutions-for-the-long-term> . Funny enough, the words Bold and Moment appear in proximity within the playbook: “*Create a sense of urgency for bold action. Share stories about how other institutions are responding to the moment to inspire action.*”
- [7] This link takes you to my universities upgraded vision and provides some insights into its budget transformation: <https://momentous.rice.edu/sites/g/files/bxs5571/files/2024-09/rIce-strategic-plan-momentous-2024.pdf> . Not all budget 'details' were deemed 'fit for public consumption'. For example, the exact dollar amounts put on student heads to determine budget allocations amongst departments. Those details were made clear to faculty and staff in 'internal' documents.
- [8] Susan Haack (2022), <https://againstprofphil.org/2022/09/25/a-guest-essay-by-susan-haack-universities-research-imperative-paying-the-price-for-perverse-incentives/>. Preposterism is the announcement of dramatic expected results way ahead of the work that may or may not lead to them.

Clips & quotes from the movie *Wall Street*, directed by Oliver Stone who may sue my university for copyright infringement. It would be ironic if Artificial Intelligence (AI) was involved in generating branding slogans that, at best, borrow from a movie script, given how every university under the sun, mine included, is advertising that they will lead in the development of 'responsible AI'.